

Survival of Tardigrade Culture in a Simulated Lunar Environment

Camila I. Tejera Roger, Emibet Ríos Roldán, José A. Santos Ramos, Sorilys Olmeda Pérez,
and Verónica Rodríguez González

STAR Academy at Arecibo Observatory - Spring 2022

May 17, 2022

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Abstract

Regolith, a weak atmosphere, and extreme temperatures are just some of the hazardous conditions that prevent life on the Moon. Research has been conducted on extremophiles and their adaptability to celestial bodies. Thus, this study aims to expand on previous findings and test whether tardigrades can thrive on the Moon. To prove the hypothesis which states that the tardigrades *Hypsibius exemplaris* would be able to survive on the Moon, they were subjected to harsh environmental conditions that resembled those found there. The experiment was conducted in the most efficient way possible with the materials accessible. Some of the Moon's most severe traits weren't able to be exactly recreated but were done in the closest way possible. The simulated environment focused mainly on three factors of the Moon, specifically the Peary Crater: its soil, vacuum, and temperature. The tardigrades were exposed to this environment for a limited time and then observed. After being exposed to some of the Moon's properties, the tardigrades observed showed signs of life. Cryptobiosis, a process that slows down the tardigrade's functioning, allowed it to survive. The results indicate that tardigrades provide the necessary traits to sustain themselves on the Moon. Further research should be conducted to fully understand the tardigrade's capabilities and their potential for space colonization.

Keywords

- **tardigrade**
 - **extremophiles**
 - **lunar environment**
 - **Peary Crater**
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Introduction

For quite some time, through space exploration, scientists have sought to expand life's horizons outside of Earth. As a result, in recent years the prospect of life on the Moon has picked these researchers' curiosity. Given the extremely harsh environmental conditions on the Moon, such as radiation, lunar dust, vacuum, cosmic rays, and extreme temperature changes, no evidence of life as it is known to have been found. Several experiments have been conducted to search for any organisms suitable for survival in a lunar environment. A previous research study tested the tolerance of cyanobacteria to various celestial bodies. The results of such a study concluded that certain cyanobacteria could survive in a lunar-like environment for short periods (Olsson-Francis, Cockell, 2010). Based on the possibility of life on the Moon, the question of whether any other organism could survive arose. This research aims to answer such a question. Various types of existing extremophiles with the potential to survive on the Moon were studied. The tardigrades, invertebrates that are tolerant to extreme terrestrial environments, demonstrated the best potential.

Therefore, this research study hypothesizes that tardigrades are capable of surviving in a lunar-like environment. An experiment where tardigrades were exposed to extreme environmental conditions, simulating the Moon, was conducted to validate such a hypothesis. To recreate the lunar environment in this experiment, several factors were taken into consideration: the Moon's regolith, atmosphere, and temperature. To replicate these factors, materials that closely matched those found on the Moon were chosen. The tardigrades were then introduced to this environment where their behavior was monitored. This research intends to find a microorganism that can survive in the harsh conditions of the Moon. The data collected during this stage resulted to be favorable to this investigation.

Theoretical Framework

Lunar Environment

When talking about the lunar environment, reference is made to the main parameters that distinguish its composition. Due to the extraordinary conditions on its surface, no active life has been currently confirmed inhabiting its territory. Among the aspects to be discussed are its temperature, atmosphere, and soil.

Regolith

On the surface of the moon, a powdery substance known as regolith can be found covering the underlying bedrock that makes up the Moon's surface. Regolith is a combination of several different minerals that have been randomly distributed as a result of meteorite bombardment. The most prevalent components that can be found in regolith are silicates plagioclase feldspar $(Ca, Na)(Al, Si)_4O_8$, pyroxene $(Ca, Fe, Mg)_2Si_2O_6$, and olivine $(Mg, Fe)_2SiO_4$ (Lucey, 2006). In the lunar soil, multiple particles must be taken into consideration, such as rock fragments, monominerals, and different types of glass. Agglutinated particles and droplets of various sources can also be found within the different types of glass.

Atmosphere

Contrary to popular beliefs, the moon does have an atmosphere, containing gasses such as sodium, potassium, and smaller amounts of helium, argon, neon, ammonia, methane, and carbon dioxide. Unlike Earth's atmosphere, the Moon has a surface boundary exosphere. This means that the atmosphere is so thin that molecules rarely collide with one another (Dunbar, 2013). Its atmosphere is solid and rocky, and it has the presence of craters and basins. Since it is weak and almost non-existent, it does not provide any protection against

the impact of asteroids, meteorites, or other celestial bodies, which makes the risk of collision with it constant (Melosh J, 1989). The lunar atmosphere isn't stable; it varies constantly. This is because, during lunar nights, the pressure can decrease to extreme levels, and it can increase during the day. Lunar temperatures can oscillate between 284 °F and -275 °F, in addition to having elevated levels of ionizing radiation from the Sun and cosmic rays (Schuerger C, 2019).

Temperature

The Moon's atmosphere does not absorb sunlight, which causes the surface to get very hot. This also causes sunlight to escape its atmosphere. The reasons listed above are why the Moon's extreme temperature varies greatly, ranging from 260°F(127°C) when sunlight hits its surface to -280°F(-173°C) when the sun goes down.

Peary Crater

It is an irregular-shaped crater situated at the north pole of the Moon (88.5°N, 30°E) which was created as a consequence of an asteroid impact. It is approximately 73 km wide, and it is considered one of the most suitable locations for a potential lunar settlement, as it lacks a sunset due to the Moon's extremely small axial tilt, causing certain spots of this crater to be illuminated with almost constant sunlight (Dunbar, 2009). Nevertheless, there are also zones with permanent shadows, as well as in other craters located at the lunar poles.

Microorganisms

They are organisms that, because of their size, can only be seen under a microscope. Also called "microbes", these organisms have a very elementary organization, counting four basic types: bacteria, protozoa, algae, and fungi. They can exist in their unicellular form or a colony of cells, and the field of science in charge of studying them is called microbiology.

(Stainer, 1978). The reason microorganisms were considered for this experiment is that their genotype is simpler compared to other more complex organisms, which makes them better candidates since they require fewer factors for their survival.

Extremophiles

An extremophile is an organism with the ability to survive in environments with extreme conditions, which would give them a greater capacity for resistance, opening up the possibility of their survival in space. (Weronika, Lukasz, 2017). They are subdivided into different categories ranging from *acidophiles* to *psychrophiles*, and *thermophiles*. They are found in all kinds of places and can withstand radioactivity, cold, intense heat, and acidity. Some of the extremophiles researched for investigation purposes were the bacterial family known as cyanobacteria, the *deinococcus radiodurans*, and the tardigrades.

Cyanobacteria. Cyanobacteria are a group of microscopic organisms capable of photosynthesis on their own, which endows them with the possibility of a role in space agriculture (more specifically, lunar) in the future. The cyanobacteria that will be considered are the following: *phormidium*, *gloeocapsa*, *leptolyngbya*, and *chroococciopsis*. However, there are more varieties possible to use in this experiment, including some bacteria of the family *sphingomonas*: *genus sphingomonas desiccabilis*, *subtilis*, and *metallidurans*. The first one attracts attention, that is because, according to the results of the BioRock experiment, it is the least affected by gravity changes, making it quite efficient in terms of biomineralization (Cockell, 2020).

Tardigrades. Among the extremophiles that have been studied, the tardigrades stand out. Tardigrades are a little-studied phylum of animals that are mostly transparent and measure from a quarter to half of a millimeter long. They have a simple body, four legs, and a pharynx that resembles a pharynx from *C. elegans*. They are found in water and are common

in beach sediments. Tardigrades have been studied for their ability to perform cryptobiosis, also called “tun”, in which state they can survive years without water. The tun is resistant to extreme temperature and when exposed to water again, the tardigrades rehydrate and “come back to life” in a short period. They are one of the most promising and cutting-edge organisms when it comes to resisting all space conditions, whether freezing temperatures, radiation, vacuum, or lack of oxygen and water, their complex structure allows them to remain indifferent. (Weronika, Łukasz, 2017). The characteristics stated above are why it is reasonable to infer that these extremophiles have the necessary components to survive and thrive in the hostile lunar environment.

Methodology

For this research project, experimentation is necessary to acquire tangible data that will provide the possibility that life on the Moon is a future reality. The team has therefore decided to build a small-scale model of Peary Crater. The model, whose proportions would be small, must be exposed to extremely low temperatures and a low-pressure environment. Extremophiles with the potential to withstand lunar circumstances, as determined by this study, will be subjected to this environment.

Materials

Preceding the experiment, the materials that would be used were gathered from various sources (see Figure 1, Figure 2, and Figure 3). The tardigrades were ordered from a biological supply company that delivered the culture the next day after making the transaction to assure the organisms would arrive in good health and guarantee that the environment they were in was well preserved. Even so, they were used seven (7) days after

arriving. The solid carbon dioxide was acquired the day of the experiment and placed in a styrofoam cooler with newspaper to ensure it would last the experiment phase (see Figure 4) while the lunar regolith simulant was provided by one of our mentors. It was sterilized under 270 degrees Fahrenheit for five (5) minutes using a pouch cycle in a dental sterilization industrial appliance to exterminate any other organisms that could live in the dust as it was notified to us that the exact composition of it was unknown and could be contaminated. The examination was carried out in the residence of one of the team members during the afternoon to keep surveillance of the investigation and facilitate the observation process. On the day of the experiment, safety equipment was adopted to take precautions for the team's health and to make certain the experiment would not be impaired as to being contaminated by any impurities that could be transferred, this included: sterile latex gloves, sterile face masks, and thermally insulated gloves.

Preparation

Once ready to commence with the second experiment phase, the materials that came in contact with the tardigrade samples were sterilized with a UV sterilizer, the following were: transparent plastic cups, a plastic pipette, microscope slides, and the measuring spoon. Three (3) plastic cups had the upper half cut with scissors and thrown away to facilitate observation and regulate size. The bottom half of these plastic cups were used as a container for the tardigrades. 3 milliliters of the microorganisms were taken out of their container with a pipette and poured into every bottom cup (see Figure 5). Beforehand, a sample of the tardigrade liquid was taken from the container and looked under a microscope to ensure they were alive and present (see Figure 6). Two (2) of the cups functioned as the experimental group and the cup left would be the control. Each of the cups in the experimental group had $\frac{1}{4}$ of a teaspoon of lunar regolith simulant poured into them (see Figure 7). After conducting

multiple tests, it was determined that a 1:3 ratio would allow the concentration of tardigrades to be greater and hence more detectable when mixed with lunar dust that is proportionally larger than the tardigrades. Then, the two (2) cups were shaken slightly to mix the tardigrade and lunar dust solution (see Figure 8). The experimental group cups were placed in their microscale vacuum chambers to lower the pressure and create a similar vacuum to the one in space. Each one was placed in the vacuum base plate platform, covered with the polycarbonate bell jar, and then connected to the “T” hose with check valves and quick-connect fitting tubing to the base plate platform with the “O” ring. The syringe functioned as a plunger to drain the air out of the vacuum chamber and release it out the other end of the tubing. Progressively, the movement of the plunger became more resistant, meaning the environment in the vacuum chamber would be each time closer to reaching a vacuum. Once the movement of the plunger was notably difficult, the second stage of the tubing was removed from the first check valve to be left with only the first stage of the tubing connected to the vacuum (see Figure 9). If the first stage was removed, the vacuum would be reestablished to the initial with-air state. Low pressure inside the vacuum chamber can be remarked when observing the tardigrade solution and noticing bubbles forming on the surface of the liquid (see Figure 10).

Experiment

After removing the second stage tubing, the vacuum chambers were covered with paper towels and secured in place with tape; this was done to prevent direct contact from the vacuum chamber to the dry ice and potentially protect the vacuum from cracking or damaging by the acute cold temperatures (see Figure 11). Subsequently, the experimental group was ready to enter the final factor of the lunar ambient simulation: dry ice inside the styrofoam cooler with a recorded temperature of -109 degrees Fahrenheit and covered with

newspaper to fill the space and preserve the cold. Using the thermally insulated gloves, the lid of the styrofoam cooler was opened, the newspaper was taken out, the dry ice bag was opened, and using the kitchen clamps, space was made to fit the two vacuum chambers into the dry ice. The two vacuum chambers were inserted into the spaces created and then covered with the dry ice to ensure it was receiving the cold from each angle (see Figure 12). They were then enclosed with the newspaper and with the lid in the styrofoam cooler. Meanwhile, the control group was left untouched in the outdoor room (see Figure 13) at 84 degrees Fahrenheit, covered with a plastic cup that was not cut in half to prevent insects or other impurities from contaminating the control group cup. Both groups were left untouched, and the experiment ran for 1 hour. After the hour ended, the lid of the styrofoam cooler was removed along with the newspaper. With the use of thermally insulated gloves, the vacuum chambers were removed from the dry ice (see Figure 14).

Observations

Because the groups were discovered frozen (see Figure 15), they were placed at room temperature at 81 degrees Fahrenheit to unfreeze and settle. This permitted the sedimentation of the solution to settle to the bottom of the cup and the liquid of the tardigrades to move to the top to facilitate observations later. After 30 minutes, the third (3) phase commenced, and the observations began. A sample of the experimental group's tardigrade culture was taken using the pipette and poured into a microscope slide. On this slide, it was important to pour mostly liquid solution and not much of the lunar dust as a result of it making observations and distinguishing tardigrades difficult. To avoid suctioning the sediment, it was best to collect liquid from the top of the solution rather than the bottom. When looking under the microscope, the observation started with a 4x objective and worked up to 40x. The experimental group was then left for seven (7) hours at room temperature to return to their

normal state due to the period it would take the tardigrades to wake up from their “tun” state. After that period passed, the observation process was repeated for the experimental group and the control group.

Table 1

Table of materials used in the experiment

Materials	General description	Assets	Disadvantages
Tardigrades (<i>Hypsibius exemplaris</i> , strain Z151)	<i>Hypsibius exemplaris</i> is a species of tardigrade in the family <i>Hypsibiidae</i> . They're known to be the "standard" tardigrades and are used in several research projects. They prefer freshwater lakes and rivers.	It is an easily accessible tardigrade, which is why it was utilized to provide an approximate overview of the tolerance of tardigrades in the lunar environment that was recreated.	Given the fact that this tardigrade has a simple genomic, its tolerance to stress is not as strong as other tardigrade species.
8lbs of Solid carbon dioxide (Dry ice)	Carbon dioxide in a solid-state with a temperature of -109° F. It lasts for around 24 hours before it sublimates.	It was used to simulate temperatures on the Moon since it was the nearest temperature to which it was accessible.	The dry ice did not exactly replicate the temperature on the Moon due to the extremely low temperatures. Additionally, the experiment was confined to one day due to its

			sublimation.
Lunar regolith simulant	It is unsterilized dust that aims to emulate the characteristics found in the lunar regolith.	Given the accessibility, it was employed as an efficient method to recreate the lunar regolith to perform our experimentation.	It cannot imitate the real lunar regolith perfectly, in addition, because it was unsterilized, there were found some minerals which are not present in the lunar regolith, damaging its precision.
7oz Transparent plastic cups	A regular plastic cup that was cut in half to fit into the vacuum chamber.	They were used to contain the control and experimental groups.	Glass cups would've been the preferred choice, but what was accessible were plastic cups.
3.5 in Microscale Vacuum Apparatus	A tool which removes the air and the pressure through the absorption and expulsion of the air through syringes.	It served as a tool that helped the experiment to simulate both the vacuum of space and the lack of oxygen in the lunar atmosphere.	It was limited in size, which made it difficult to append extra resources to emulate other atmospheric factors studied.
3ml Plastic pipette dropper	A tool that measures and transports liquids from one area to another	This was utilized to accurately measure the tardigrade culture used in	n/a

		the experiment.	
30 Quart Styrofoam cooler	A container used as a portable refrigerator to maintain the coolness of beverages and for storing ice.	This was used to maintain the dry ice and vacuum chamber insulated.	It was not the best way to maintain them insulated but it was what was accessible.
Newspaper	A type of paper produced with a mixture of recycled material and wood pulp.	Filled the gaps in the styrofoam container so that the dry ice could last longer without sublimating.	n/a
Microscope (4x,10x,40x objectives)	An instrument used to enhance microscopic objects with magnifications of 40x, 100x, and 400x.	This instrument allowed tardigrades to be observed and examined.	The microscope used in this experiment does not reach the maximum magnification level that a light microscope can achieve.
Clear glass microscope slides	A flat, thin piece of glass, usually 75mm by 26mm and about 1mm thick, used to hold objects to be examined under a microscope.	These slides were used to analyze materials for the experiment.	n/a
¼ tsp Metal measuring spoon	An appliance used to measure the amount of an ingredient.	These were used to measure the lunar dust.	n/a

Scissors	A cutting utensil that has two blades whose cutting edges slide past each other.	Instrument used to cut plastic cups.	This was not the most precise way to cut the cups.
Latex gloves	A glove made of latex, which is a biodegradable ingredient that originates from the latex ducts of rubber trees.	This was used as a form of protection as well as to prevent contamination of any materials to be used in the experiment.	n/a
Thermally insulated gloves	A glove that protects frostnip and frostbite.	These were used to protect the hands when manipulating the dry ice.	n/a
Paper towels	A soft, thick sheet of paper that can absorb liquid and is used to dry hands, and wipe up spills, among other things.	Used to shroud the vacuum chambers to prevent direct contact with the dry ice.	This was the easiest manner to avoid direct contact, but not the best.
Kitchen Clamps	Tongs are used to pick up objects, generally food.	Used to make space for the vacuum chambers in the dry ice.	They were difficult to manipulate.
Plastic bag	A container made of a thin, flexible, plastic film that is open at one end.	This was used to accommodate the dry ice inside the cooler.	The thin material that they're made of may cause the bag to rupture.
Clear plastic tape	An object made of the thermoplastic polymer polypropylene or polyvinyl chloride is used to attach to certain objects.	This was utilized to secure the paper towels to the vacuum chamber.	It is not the most dependable tape, but it was the one accessible

Results

The experiment conducted focused primarily on testing whether tardigrades belonging to the species *Hypsibius exemplaris* would be able to survive an environment similar to the Moon. However, given the impossibility of collecting some of the materials required, the recreation of the environment was not entirely accurate. Therefore, experimenting with a previous manner achieved the following results. Before the seven (7) hours were initiated, the first observations were made to the experimental group during the night (considering the experiment started in the afternoon) after leaving the tardigrade solution unfreeze. In these, it was hard to distinguish tardigrades from the lunar dust. Only one (1) tardigrade was seen moving in a rather quick motion, this organism was located behind the second (2) tardigrade spotted (see Figure 16), this one was motionless when examined. For this, it was inferred they were in their “tun” state and decided to establish a time for the tardigrades to go to their previous moving form. After the tardigrades and lunar dust simulant solution melted to its original liquid state posterior to the seven (7) hours given, the experimental group was examined again under a microscope exactly as performed and described during the third (3) phase of the experiment.

It is imperative to note that when searching for tardigrades in the experimental group solution, regardless of the ratio of solute to solvent, the organisms did not appear in an instant continuously or from the first time observed. The lamellae or slide must be moved around to examine and cover all the area available with the sample because the tardigrades mix with the dust and become hidden. Another factor is the size of the dust particles makes observing tardigrades a challenge, especially when they are not moving. The tardigrades were spotted mostly when noticing movement and then focusing on the area. They were seen usually feeding on *algae* or close to it. In the wave of observations made during the morning of the second day of the experiment, after the seven (7) hours, six (6) tardigrades were found alive

and moving without having to be deeply inspected for much time (see Figure 17, Figure 18 and Figure 19). Likewise, the control group was sampled and examined under the microscope, as expected, one (1) tardigrade was seen immediately moving near algae (see Figure 20).

As observed through the microscope, it can be inferred that tardigrades, although coiled and motionless, remain alive in their “tun” state. This settlement can be deduced taking into consideration previous observations where the organisms can be noted still and unmoving but after the time passed they could be seen alive and “healthy”. In addition, it can also be concluded that tardigrades used a method of cryptobiosis called "cryobiosis", a survival mechanism that takes place as a reaction to the decrease in temperature. (Clegg, 2001). This mechanism is initiated at the moment that the water envelopes the cells of the frozen tardigrade. The disruption of the mobility of the molecules causes the organism to withstand the freezing temperatures until more hospitable conditions return. This experiment demonstrated that tardigrades are capable of surviving low temperatures and low-pressure environments, in addition to the simulated soil materials. In other words, the tardigrades have the proven resources required for effective sustainability in a lunar-like environment.

Discussion

Different factors such as fluctuating temperatures, lunar dust, and the lack of a proper atmosphere, make the Moon a harmful place for some organisms to survive. Therefore, an experiment using tardigrades was conducted to test whether these microorganisms could survive in an environment similar to the Moon. The results of this experiment concluded that tardigrades were able to survive the following factors to which they were exposed: cold temperatures (-109° F), a vacuum, and lunar dust. After long processes in which these

microorganisms were tested, the pertinent variables were managed to conduct the experiment as reliably as possible. The mode of handling by which the tardigrades were exposed to the aforementioned factors was by placing them on a lunar dust surface, located inside a vacuum chamber under low temperatures produced by the effect of dry ice in an enclosed environment.

In line with the hypothesis, the tardigrades were able to survive due to their adaptability to harsh conditions. Once exposed to these factors, they went into their “tun” state, a state that causes their metabolism to only require 0.01 percent of what it would normally require, thus preparing the tardigrades for the absence of food caused by the low temperatures. This process makes tardigrades able to survive in this state for extended periods and be capable of resisting more extreme temperatures, but because of the reversibility of their “tun” state, the *Hypsibius exemplaris* can return to its usual behavior once its temperature has been regulated to a suitable state. Tardigrades generate a defense mechanism known as cryobiosis. It is activated when exposed to low temperatures, in this case, freezing. Cryobiosis is present at every stage of a tardigrade’s growth, providing them the ability to survive harsh conditions. This process has been proven beneficial to the tardigrades in several other experiments (Weronika, Lukasz, 2017). Therefore, making tardigrades a perfect candidate for separate space investigations.

When searching for a potential organism capable of successfully surviving lunar conditions, this research’s results should be taken into consideration. In the case where *Hypsibius exemplaris* continues to exhibit favorable characteristics in such an environment in further experiments, it might open a door into the realm of lunar colonization. Since the tardigrades are suitable to tolerate severe temperatures and very low pressures, it would imply the possibility that such organisms possess the ability to survive an environment similar to the Moon. New studies on the survival methods that these organisms utilize can benefit humans

in different areas. For example, to understand the chemical and physiological function executed by tardigrades, further studies on the different types of cryptobiosis performed are necessary. This knowledge would be advantageously used to help humankind become capable of surviving under more extreme environmental conditions, such as the lunar ones. Introducing certain genes that control the ability of tardigrades to withstand extreme conditions to the DNA of plants in potential future space exploration missions could become a key component in their survival (Bittel, 2016).

The lunar conditions replicated in this experiment weren't precisely those found on the Moon due to the inaccessibility to the materials needed. As a result of this, the experiment was conducted with those materials accessible. Another factor to take into consideration is that the Moon boasts an extremely low and fluctuating temperature, with an average of -457.6°F , the reason for which finding the necessary resources to experiment with the ideal temperature was a challenge. Therefore the research was guided around the selected reference point, Peary Crater, which has a temperature range between -238°F to 212°F . The experiment was conducted with the implication that the spot remained at its cold temperature, which is why the team decided to go forward and utilize dry ice (with a temperature of -109°F), since it is sufficiently cold to recreate a cool environment, in an attempt to emulate the lunar temperature. Despite continuous attempts to access laboratory facilities, the process proved to be more problematic than expected, resulting in the inability to perform the procedures in the preferred environment, a factor that could have been beneficial in conducting the experiment. As a result, it was determined that the most appropriate place to conduct the experiment in this situation was at the residence of one of the team members, where the highest levels of sterilization possible were tried to be maintained given the conditions. Thus, the surroundings weren't ideal for conducting procedures that required a controlled environment. An additional factor that influenced the performance and precision of the experimental set-up and thus the

results of the experiment was the unfortunate occurrence of the vacuum seal rupturing. The “O” ring of the vacuum chamber base lost its seal as a result of the low temperatures, causing the low-pressure environment created for the tardigrades to be disrupted. Despite this, it can be inferred that the sample of the tardigrade culture froze while the vacuum seal was still in place.

Further research needs to be conducted on tardigrades and their sustainability on the Moon, it is recommended these experiments be conducted in a more sophisticated setting to more accurately portray the Moon. These should include lower temperatures, a more consistent vacuum seal, and the exact illumination of the target area, given that the lunar poles exhibit variations in temperature and illumination caused by a variety of factors that have already been studied. It is also suggested that such experiments should not be limited to testing the survival of *Hypsibius exemplaris*, but should seek to test the resistance of other types of tardigrades with more complete physiological systems. Testing these organisms in settings from different areas of the Moon would be beneficial to observe how those changes may or may not affect the *Hypsibius exemplaris* or any other types of tardigrades that were to be examined. Lastly, more precise observations throughout the experiment of the organisms being surveyed are also recommended for future investigations.

Conclusion

Most species are unable to survive on the Moon due to its exceedingly hazardous environment. Nevertheless, there is a possibility that extremophiles, which are organisms that withstand extreme conditions here on Earth, may have the necessary adaptability to exist on the Moon. This led the team to start researching possible extremophiles that may have the proper characteristics to sustain themselves in a lunar-like environment. One extremophile

that was found to have all of the necessary qualities to survive in a lunar environment is the tardigrade *Hypsibius exemplaris*, microscopic invertebrates that can be found in mosses, lichens, and soil. When these are exposed to extreme conditions they go into their cryptobiotic state, also known as their “tun” state, which helps them to protect their internal organs and reduces the amount of water lost through transpiration. Considering the characteristics the tardigrades exhibited, they were selected for experimentation in a lunar-like environment. This lunar environment was built to enable us to simulate some of the fundamental characteristics of the moon, such as temperature, vacuum, and soil. After the experimentation, the tardigrades were observed under the microscope, which revealed they exhibited motion and life signs and it was proved they could withstand the simulated lunar environment, as stipulated.

To address the problem stated, an experiment plan was organized, and the steps followed can be narrowed down to 3 phases: preparation, experiment, and observation phase. During the preparation phase, the materials to be used were sterilized and organized, and the tardigrades were separated into their respective containers and searched under a microscope to ensure movement to indicate life. Phase two or the experimental phase began when the control and experiment groups were established and placed under the conditions they were assigned, these are the control in a normal environment and the experimental group in the lunar simulation ambient where the two would stay for one (1) hour. This lunar environment was built to enable the simulation of some of the fundamental characteristics of the moon, such as temperature, vacuum, and soil. The conditions where said organisms would be expected to live if they were on the Moon were researched, and based on the findings it was stipulated the best way to get to that point. Following the second phase, the observation stage was assigned to collect the results and data of the experiment, this included the finding of life, characteristics of the experiment, and sudden details that emerged along the process. The

gradual changes in the tardigrades were observed after being under the conditions and their behavior the day after the experiment. In unison with the hypothesis, the tardigrades presented signs of life and proved they could withstand the simulated lunar environment.

More research into the adaptability of extremophiles on the Moon is required. This type of research could help scientists get closer to their aim of lunar colonization. Lunar agriculture may become prosperous if the tardigrade's chemical and physiological functions were better understood. Certain genes that control the ability of tardigrades to withstand extreme conditions can be introduced to the DNA of plants in potential future space exploration missions and could become the key component in their survival. With this knowledge, humankind may become capable of surviving under more extreme environmental conditions, such as the lunar ones.

Acknowledgments

This research would not have been possible without the irreplaceable opportunity given to us by the STAR Academy Staff to participate in this program. We would like to extend our gratitude for their guidance and support throughout this academically enriching process. It is of utmost importance for us to express our sincere appreciation to Yasmin Santiago, for supplying the vacuum chambers and lunar regolith that allowed us to conduct the experiment successfully. It is recognizable the importance of Zaian López's mentorship, for her consistent feedback on how we could improve our work in order to make us better writers and scientists. The group would also like to acknowledge the help of Bradley Rivera during the brainstorming process, which steered us to conduct our experiment in the most efficient way possible. It is our desire to also extend our gratitude to our parents for supporting us for the entire duration of this project. Finally, we will always be grateful for

this joyful journey that led us to form new friendships and memories alongside our group members and participants of STAR Academy.

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Appendix A

Images of figures referenced throughout the paper

Figure 1

Materials Used in the Experiment 1.0

Note. Few of the materials used for the experiment: lunar regolith simulant in the sterilized bags, surgical gloves, microscale vacuum apparatus, 3 plastic cups cut in half, plastic pipette, tape, tardigrade solution in its container, and paper towels.

Figure 2

Materials used in the experiment 1.1

Note. Few of the materials used for the experiment: quart styrofoam cooler with dry ice and newspaper inside, scissors, kitchen clamps, and thermally insulated gloves.

Figure 3

Materials Used in the Experiment 1.2

Note. Few of the materials used for the experiment (these were sterilized): measuring spoons and three glass slides.

Figure 4

Materials Used in the Experiment 1.3

Note. 8lbs of dry ice in the shape of small cylinders inside the plastic bag and styrofoam cooler for transportation and insulation.

Figure 5

Tardigrade liquid inside half plastic cups

Note. 3ml of the tardigrade culture liquid poured in the three half cut plastic containers.

Figure 6

Tardigrade observation before experiment

Note. This is what was seen under the microscope when taking a sample of the tardigrade liquid in the container they came in to assure they were alive before proceeding with the experiment.

Figure 7

Pouring lunar dust simulant into the experimental group

Note. Incorporation of $\frac{1}{4}$ tsp. of the regolith simulant into the two experimental group cups with the tardigrade liquid.

Figure 8

Tardigrade liquid and lunar regolith simulant solution

Note. A closer look into the experimental group tardigrade and lunar dust solution.

Figure 9

Experimental group with low pressure achieved

Note. The experimental group is inside the two microscale vacuum apparatus with only the first stage of the tubing connected as an effect of the low pressure environment being reached, it is ready to be covered with paper towels.

Figure 10

Low-pressure effects on the tardigrade solution

Note. Bubbles developing in water as caused when creating a low pressure environment by eliminating as much air as possible.

Figure 11

Precautionary measures taken into consideration

Note. The vacuum chambers are covered with paper towels to prevent direct contact with the dry ice as precaution to avoid possible cracking of the plastic surface.

Figure 12

Vacuum chambers inserted in the dry ice

Note. The vacuum chambers are inserted in the designated dry ice spots and surrounded by it to assure it receives cold from every angle.

Figure 13

Control Group

Note. A closer look into the control group, it contains the tardigrade liquid in the half plastic cup.

Figure 14

Experimental group once taken out of the dry ice

Note. The vacuum chamber after being left in the dry ice cooler and then taken out one (1) hour later.

Figure 15

Frozen Tardigrade Solution

Note. The experimental group after its time in the dry ice can be appreciated to be frozen along with the “O” ring; the freezing of the “O” ring caused the vacuum seal to rupture.

Figure 16

Observation before the 7 hours

Note. This image presents the first observation done on a sample after being taken out of the dry ice and left to unfreeze. Circled in red, a tardigrade in its “tun” state lays unmobile while circled in blue is a tardigrade that was moving when seen under the microscope and in the video taken.

Figure 17

Observations after the 7 hours 1.0

Note. In the image can be appreciated, circled in blue the two (2) tardigrades being observed under a microscope after noticing a sign of motility.

Figure 18

Observations after the 7 hours 1.1

Note. In this particular image, three (3) tardigrades can be seen faintly when circled in blue, when observing under a microscope, the movement can be detected easily but obtaining a clear and concise image can be difficult. All of the presented were moving and not in their “tun” state.

Figure 19

Observations after the 7 hours 1.2

Note. This image presents another example of the difficulties when intending to capture images of tardigrades under a microscope, the tardigrade circled in blue was moving well and did not present symptoms of being in a “tun” state.

Figure 20

Control group observations after 7 hours of the experiment

Note. This image taken from the control group of the experiment after the seven (7) hours, presents a tardigrade that showed clear motility and no signs of being in the “tun” state.